

Speciation of L-ornithine complexes of cobalt-, copper- and zinc(II) in water-dimethylformamide mixtures

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Speciation of L-ornithine complexes of Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} has been investigated in 0–60% (v/v) water-*N,N'*-dimethylformamide media pH-metrically. The predominant species formed are CoL₂H₂²⁺, CuL₂H₂²⁺, CuL₂H₄⁴⁺ and ZnL₂H⁺ in addition to ML⁺, ML₂ and MLH²⁺ for all the metals. The trend of stability constants with the solvent parameters shows the complexity of equilibria. The inclusion of solvent and water molecules in equilibria gives a complete picture of the speciation studies.

Ornithine, in mammals, forms precursors for the synthesis of L-arginine. In human colon carcinoma cells, L-Arginine is the common precursor of L-ornithine, which generates polyamines necessary for cellular growth¹. Arginase activity is regulated by various small molecules including the product, L-ornithine in liver². Feeding of adults with ornithine increases the total strength and lean body mass, and decreases urinary hydroxyproline³. Ornithine can be used in combination with manganese to achieve hypoglycemia in hyperglycemic conditions. Hyperornithinaemia-hyperammonaemia-homocitrullinuria syndrome is caused by mutations in a gene encoding a mitochondrial ornithine transporter⁴.

Divalent cobalt, copper and zinc ions act as structural promoters or are associated with active centers of enzymes. Therefore, speciation of Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with L-ornithine has been studied electrometrically. To mimic the low dielectric constant environment at the active sites of the enzymes, *N,N'*-dimethylformamide (DMF)-water mixtures were chosen as media. The study throws light on the effect of dielectric constant on the stabilities and distribution of the complexes at different pH conditions. This distribution can be interpolated/extrapolated to the biological active site if the dielectric constant of the active site is known. And the probable form of the active site can be predicted.

Results and Discussion

L-Ornithine having a carboxyl and two amino protons, acts as a tridentate ligand in complexation reactions. The protonation constants⁵ and protonation equilibria⁶ of L-ornithine indicate that the equilibria exist in the pH range 2.0–10.0 in water-DMF media.

The parameters of the best-fit models are given in Table 1 for L-ornithine complexes of Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} in water-

DMF mixture and the speciation curves obtained as MINI-QUAD75⁷ outputs are presented in Fig. 1.

Table 1. Best-fit models of M(II)-ornithine complexes in water-DMF mixtures

Temp. = 303 K, ionic strength = 0.16 mol dm⁻³, No. of titrations in each percentage = 9

DMF% (v/v)	log β _{mth} (SD)					
	110	120	111	121	122	124
Co ^{II} -ornithine (pH range = 6.0–0.0)						
00.0	5.89(7)	8.70(7)	14.07(9)	–	27.55(8)	–
10.0	5.95(4)	8.50(4)	14.15(5)	–	27.28(5)	–
20.0	6.50(6)	9.18(7)	14.24(7)	–	27.50(14)	–
30.0	6.86(6)	10.23(7)	14.14(12)	–	27.82(14)	–
40.0	6.98(5)	9.81(8)	14.00(7)	–	28.63(9)	–
50.0	7.64(4)	10.51(6)	13.95(9)	–	28.92(11)	–
60.0	7.85(6)	11.35(8)	13.78(8)	–	27.53(7)	–
Cu ^{II} -ornithine (pH range = 2.0–10.0)						
00.0	13.01(6)	15.42(7)	18.21(3)	–	34.47(7)	42.62(5)
10.0	11.07(8)	15.14(9)	17.35(5)	–	34.28(9)	40.75(9)
20.0	12.97(9)	15.27(11)	17.40(4)	–	34.37(9)	41.25(7)
30.0	13.61(7)	15.46(6)	17.71(2)	–	34.08(7)	41.94(9)
40.0	13.81(8)	15.76(10)	17.79(3)	–	33.78(7)	40.49(9)
50.0	14.66(12)	17.10(11)	18.83(4)	–	34.64(11)	41.72(9)
60.0	15.40(11)	18.77(14)	19.33(4)	–	Rej	Rej
Zn ^{II} -ornithine (pH range = 6.0–10.0)						
00.0	6.90(6)	10.35(5)	14.43(9)	19.50(11)	–	–
10.0	6.96(7)	10.36(8)	14.49(8)	19.27(10)	–	–
20.0	7.31(7)	10.45(7)	14.66(8)	19.90(9)	–	–
30.0	7.90(6)	11.27(4)	14.82(7)	20.84(8)	–	–
40.0	7.87(5)	11.63(6)	14.47(9)	20.43(9)	–	–
50.0	7.86(6)	11.68(8)	14.24(7)	20.22(9)	–	–
60.0	7.46(7)	11.69(8)	14.09(7)	19.98(10)	–	–

Fig. 1. Species distribution diagrams of (A) Co^{II}-ORN, (B) Cu^{II}-ORN, (C) Zn^{II}-ORN, in 30% DMF.

The present investigation is confined to the pH range 6.0–10.0 for the Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes. In this region the predominant forms of the ligand are found to be LH₂⁺ and LH and the probable metal-ligand species are ML, ML₂, MLH, ML₂H₂ and ML₂H. The species refined are ML, ML₂, MLH and ML₂H₂ for Co^{II}-ORN and ML, ML₂, MLH and ML₂H for Zn^{II}-ORN systems. Cu^{II} formed ML₂H₄ species along with ML, ML₂, MLH and ML₂H₂. This is quite reasonable, as at pH as low as 2.0 the ligand form is LH₃⁺. The probable equilibria of formation of complexes in the pH range of study based on the observations can be proposed as given below.

For M = Co^{II} and Zn^{II} :

6.0 < pH < 8.0 :

Fig. 2. Variation of log *K* of (A) Co^{II}-ORN, (B) Cu^{II}-ORN, (C) Zn^{II}-ORN with (Δ) mole fraction and (O) reciprocal of dielectric constant in water-DMF mixtures. (Δ, O) log *K*₁₁₀, (▲, ●) log *K*₁₂₀.

8.0 < pH < 10.0 :

Eqs. (1)–(4) are the major contributors whereas eqs. (5) and (6) contribute but very little.

For $M = Cu^{II}$, in addition to eqs. (1), (2), (4) and (5) the following additional equilibria are operative :

2.0 < pH < 4.0 :

4.0 < pH < 8.0 :

8.0 < pH < 10.0 :

Contributions of eqs. (2) and (7) are of course very small.

Effect of solvent on the stabilities of the complex species was inferred by plotting logarithmic values of step-wise stability constants ($\log K$) against reciprocal of

Fig. 3. Linearisation of $\log K$ with solvent parameter for Co^{II} -ORN in water-DMF mixtures : (O) $\log K_{110}$, (●) $\log \beta_{111}$, (▲) $\log K_{120}$, (Δ) $\log \beta_{122}$.

dielectric constant ($1/D$) or mole fraction (n_x) of DMF (Fig. 2). These plots indicate the nature of electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces operating in the equilibria. It is observed

that the variations of $\log K$ values are mostly non-linear, except for $\log k_{110}$ of Co^{II} -ORN species. The trends indicate that the interactions are complex⁸. The non-linearity can be removed by considering water and DMF molecules in the solvation sphere⁵ of the species. A plot of $\log K + j \log [S]$ vs $\log \{[H_2O]/[S]\}$ should be linear provided the change in the stability constant is strictly assignable to the variation of medium effect. Here, j is the total number of water and solvent molecules in the solvation sphere, $[H_2O]$ and $[S]$ are the concentrations of water and co-solvent. When co-solvent is highly polar or coordinating, the solvent molecules released from the coordination sphere include those of the co-solvent also. In the case of non-polar co-solvents, water will be exclusively involved in equilibria. Fig. 3 is a typical plot that indicates the linearisation of the trend due to the inclusion of both water and DMF molecules in equilibria. The change in the number of water and DMF molecules associated with each of the equilibrium is given in Table 2.

Table 2. Change in the number of water and DMF molecules in the best linear model of metal-ornithine equilibria

Species	Number of molecules involved in the equilibrium		
	Water	DMF	Total
CoL	-3.7	6.7	3
CoL ₂	-1.9	3.9	2
CoLH	3.1	-8.1	-5
CoL ₂ H ₂	2.8	-7.8	-5
CuL	-6.0	11.0	5
CuL ₂	-3.3	8.3	5
CuLH	-4.6	9.6	5
CuL ₂ H ₂	4.3	-9.3	-5
CuL ₂ H ₄	2.9	-7.9	-5
ZnL ₂	-4.1	9.1	5
ZnLH	3.8	-8.8	-5
ZnL ₂ H	3.9	-7.9	-5

Experimental

Solutions of L-ornithine hydrogen chloride (E. Merck), cobalt(II), copper(II) and zinc(II) chlorides (G.R., E. Merck) were prepared in triple-distilled water. *N,N'*-Dimethylformamide (99.5% purity, E. Merck) was used as such.

The titrations were carried out in the medium containing varying volumes of DMF (10–60%, v/v), maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol dm⁻³ with KCl at 303 ± 0.05 K. An Elico LI-120 pH meter was used. Titrations with different ratios (1 : 1.5–1 : 5.3) of metal-ligand were carried out with 0.4 mol dm⁻³ KOH. Other experimental details are given elsewhere⁹.

Approximate stability constants of the complexes of L-ornithine were calculated with the computer program SCPHD¹⁰. The best-fit chemical models were obtained using non-linear least-square analysis program MINQUAD75.

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